

Ascorbic acid-based oxidative potential of Cu, Fe and Mn soluble salts at neutral and acidic conditions

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Keywords: oxidative potential, ascorbic acid, metals, artificial lysosomal fluid, chloride.

Associated conference topics: 4.6

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The Oxidative potential (OP) of particulate matter (PM) has been widely used to predict PM toxicity. The ascorbic acid assay (OP-AA) is a widely used OP test. Numerous studies have obtained the OP-AA of PM measuring the depletion rate of ascorbate by reading its absorbance ($\lambda=265$ nm) over time. However, there are considerable doubts regarding the parameters to be applied in OP assays (Bates *et al*, 2019). One key factor, which can affect the AA oxidation catalysed by PM-bound pollutants, is the fluid type and composition used in the method. Most research has measured PM OP-AA under neutral pH conditions using phosphate buffer to maintain a neutral and constant pH value, although, different buffer compositions have been applied. Moreover, recent studies have used simulated lung fluids in the OP-AA assay to represent better the conditions in the lung. The commonly lung fluids used are: Gamble's solution (pH 7.4) and Artificial Lysosomal Fluid (ALF) (pH 4.5). The last one has been less investigated in OP assays. ALF represents the acidic fluid resulting from the attack of macrophages to the particles reaching the alveoli.

Former research highlighted that AA oxidation in the presence of metals is also affected by some species present in the reaction, such as chloride ions (Murekhina *et al*, 2022), and pH (Khan and Martell, 1967). Besides, the amount of ascorbate is lower at acidic pH (pK_a 4.12).

The purpose of this work is to better understand the effect of fluid composition and pH on ascorbate assay. To this end, the OP-AA of individual soluble metal salts ($CuSO_4$, $FeCl_3$, $FeCl_2$, $MnCl_2$) in three different fluids at a range of environmentally relevant concentrations was measured. Two neutral buffers were used: phosphate buffer (PB, 0.05M) and phosphate buffer saline (PBS1x, 0.01M, 0.1M NaCl). The main difference between these buffers is the presence of chloride in PBS. Besides, an acidic simulated lung fluid (ALF, pH 4.5) was investigated. This fluid contains different inorganic (such as NaCl and NaOH) and organic (such as glycine and citric acid) salts to mimic lung fluid constituents.

The results obtained indicate that Cu(ii), Fe(ii), Fe(iii) catalysed the AA oxidation in the three fluids. Exceptionally, Mn(ii) in all fluids across a wide range of concentrations (from 5 to 50 μM) showed a depletion

rate close to the blank value. The OP responses of metals varied in each fluid, generally, the AA responses of metals were higher in PB, followed by PBS1x and ALF. However, the variability of OP-AA depended on each metal and each fluid. As Table 1 showed, the OP-AA of Cu drastically decreased when Cu was dissolved in ALF or PBS1x compared to PB; nevertheless, the OP-AA of Fe(ii) and Fe(iii) did not decrease much in ALF and PBS1x with respect to PB.

Table 1. OP-AA of metals in the studied fluids.

Metal Conc. (μM)	OP-AA PB ($\mu M/min$)	OP-AA PBS1x ($\mu M/min$)	OP-AA ALF ($\mu M/min$)
Cu(ii) (0.5)	10.57	0.77	0.28
Fe(ii) (5)	0.31	0.20	0.18
Fe(iii) (5)	0.33	0.20	0.17

Besides, different concentrations of soluble metals were investigated to represent the usual range of atmospheric metal concentrations in urban/industrial mixed areas. The results showed that the concentration responses of almost all metals are nonlinear, although, the nonlinear behaviour changed depending on the fluid. Finally, the effect of the oxidation state of Fe on AA assay was investigated, obtaining similar values for Fe(ii) and Fe(iii) across the entire range of concentrations tested (5-50 μM) in all fluids, except for Fe(iii) in PBS1x.

In conclusion, each metal showed a different sensitivity to AA assay depending on the composition and the pH of the fluid used. So, the type and composition of fluid used in the extraction of PM should be considered in the development of the AA assay to measure suitably the OP of real PM samples, selecting the more realistic fluid that mimics the lung conditions.

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Project PID2020-428 114787RB-I00).

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